

ReBioCycle Pulse

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Feature 3/2025 – Recycling the Future: Progress in ReBioCycle Hubs, Launch of the Talk Series on Recycling Bioplastics, Open EU Consultations

ReBioCycle

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What is ReBioCycle?

ReBioCycle stands for "A new European #blueprint for circular bioplastics #upcycling solutions." It is an Innovation Action project focusing on biobased biodegradable polymers and plastics. ReBioCycle goals are to demonstrate that:

✓ **#biobased #biodegradable #plastics** can be kept in the cycle for as long as possible through innovative **#recycling** technologies

✔ [#endoflife](#) [#biobased](#) [#biodegradable](#) [#plastics](#) can be used in the [#circular](#) [#bioeconomy](#)

The project is funded by the [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. ReBioCycle started on 1 October 2024 and operated for a period of 4 years.

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Progress in the ReBioCycle Hubs Collection and Sorting activities

Over the last few months, the [ReBioCycle hubs](#) have been consolidated through discussions between partners within each Hub and across Hubs. The Hub partners have set up and share internal resources that describe material types, quantities, donors and receivers as well as the timing of material flows. The Hub assemblies will take place every 6 months to enable frequent monitoring of Hub activity and progress.

The hubs work on the application of various recycling technologies, including mechanical, chemical, and biological recycling, utilising both enzymes and microorganisms. More features on the work of the hub are presented in the ReBioCycle factsheet: <https://zenodo.org/records/14771612>

The hubs work together to produce recycled bioplastics of the same grade as the original input material or as good as virgin materials, and to maximise the highest possible efficiency in their processes.

Each of the three Hubs is currently working on the following aspects:

- National and local legislative framework, methods and state of the art of technologies to be applied for the recycling of bioplastics. This includes a comparative analysis of existing regulations in different Member States, a summary of best practices adopted, and an overview of emerging technologies that can offer more efficient and sustainable solutions.
- Qualitative and quantitative objectives for the bioplastics fraction of the ReBioCycle project: Specific targets have been defined for waste reduction, the increase in the recycling rate, and the improvement of recycled material quality. Key performance indicators (KPIs) and benchmarks have been established to track progress against established goals.
- Strategies, technologies, and operational methods to be applied to increase sustainability in the use of bioplastics. Guidelines will be detailed for the implementation of integrated waste management systems, the development of new chemical and mechanical recycling technologies, and optimal operational practices to minimise environmental impact along the entire bioplastics value chain.

The collection of bioplastics waste, its purification, and single-material stream systems in the various hubs reflect the various regional waste management setups, and each hub plan reflects those regional setups. ReBioCycle recognises the separation of materials at source, before materials reach the waste management plants, as a key factor. This approach aligns with the strategy to achieve the desired purity levels and material quality for the feed material used in chemical or biological recycling technologies. Advanced sorting technologies, enhanced contamination control measures, and the sharing of best practices will inform and improve efforts across the hubs, allowing us to generate recycled materials that meet the stringent quality requirements necessary for high-value applications. This, in turn, will foster a circular bioeconomy.

Sorted bioplastics, a sample. Courtesy of IREN Group, partner in ReBioCycle.

References

Overview of the activities in the ReBioCycle Hubs:

- Dutch Hub <https://zenodo.org/records/15803636>
- Italian hub <https://zenodo.org/records/14849446>
- Spanish Hub <https://zenodo.org/records/14849416>

Launch of the talks of the Bioplastics Recycling Cluster on "Advancements in the Recycling of Bioplastics"

Are you an expert in recycling of bioplastics, sorting or collecting? Are you working on this topic and would like to exchange with peers?

Look no further, this series of talks is for you!

When? The series starts on 9 September 2025 and will conclude in March 2026.

For whom? Peer researchers from the public and private sectors who are working on sorting, collecting and recycling bioplastics.

Your benefits:

- Develop further your knowledge and expertise
- Connect with peers
- Discover possibilities for collaborations

europa**bioplastics**

Bioplastics Recycling Cluster Talks

How can we establish cost-competitive bioplastic sorting and recycling systems?

m2BIOS

ReBioCycle

Circular
Bio-based
Europe
Joint Undertaking

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

Co-funded by
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PROSPER

Calendar of the talks

Tuesday 9 September 2025: New technologies and digital tools for collecting and sorting bioplastics: NIR technologies. Speakers: [Carles Musoll](#) PICVISA and [Gemma Figuerola Miró](#), LEITAT, MoeBIOS

Tuesday 7 October 2025: Digital tools for sorting. Speaker: Antoine Bourely, PELLENC

Tuesday 4 November 2025: Design for Recycling criteria for bioplastics packaging. Speakers: [Lorette Du Preez](#), European Bioplastics and [Laura Tirkkonen-Rajasalo](#) SULAPAC, ReBioCycle

Tuesday 13 January 2026: PLA sorting model. Speaker: [Wang Li](#), Univ. Ghent, PROSPER

Tuesday 3 February 2026: Microbial recycling for bioplastics. Speaker: [João Sousa](#), Paques Biomaterials, ReBioCycle

Tuesday 3 March 2026: The certification scheme OK Recycled certification and labelling. Speaker: [Giulia Finazzi](#), TÜV Austria Italy – ReBioCycle and MoeBIOS advisor

How to register for the talks?

Go to this page and register for the single talks: <https://www.eventbrite.com/cc/bioplastics-recycling-cluster-talks-4428313>

The series runs from September 2025 to March 2026. A second edition will resume in September 2026 with a new calendar of talks

Meet our partner at Trinity College Dublin: Pooja Priyadarsini

A **three-minute** interview with our colleague Pooja, a research assistant working in the team at Trinity College Dublin. The team at Trinity College is specialised in the pre-treatment technologies and the mechanical recycling of biodegradable plastics.

<https://youtu.be/g04hXz8UPyl>

Interview with
Pooja Priyadarsini
Trinity College Dublin

ReBioCycle Project Partner

Presented by **europeanbioplastics**

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Call for evidence on the upcoming Circular Economy Act

The European Commission launched a public consultation and a call for evidence to gather views from the public and experts for the upcoming Circular Economy Act. The feedback gathered will provide the Commission with a better understanding of the bottlenecks and the opportunities in advancing the circular economy in Europe. The Circular Economy Act will accelerate this transition, enhancing the EU's economic security, resilience, competitiveness and decarbonisation.

Due for adoption in 2026, the Act will establish a single market for secondary raw materials and increase the supply of high-quality recycled materials – all while stimulating demand for these materials in the EU. This follows the recommendations from the [Letta](#) and [Draghi](#) reports, the industry ([Antwerp Declaration](#)), the European Council ([Budapest Declaration](#)), and the European Parliament. The Circular Economy Act will contribute to the goals set out in the [Competitiveness Compass](#) and the [Clean Industrial Deal](#) to make the EU the world leader in circular economy by 2030 and to double EU circularity rate. Experts can participate in the online consultation at the Commission's [Have Your Say](#) portal until **6 November 2025**.

Revised Framework for 'Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)' Chemicals and Materials

The European Commission Recommendation establishing a European assessment framework for 'safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials' ([C/2022/8854](#)) was adopted in December 2022. The Recommendation laid out a comprehensive framework for supporting the design, development, production and use of chemicals and materials that provide desired functions or services while being safer and more sustainable, thereby guaranteeing better protection of human health and the environment throughout their entire life cycle.

The 2022 European Commission Recommendation sets a testing period during which Member States, industry, academia and research and technology organisations were able to test and give their feedback on the assessment framework via a voluntary reporting mechanism. The testing period went through two consultation and reporting cycles, one in 2023 and a second one in 2024. During the two-year testing period, more than 80 case studies were reported, analysed and discussed. Moreover, two stakeholders' workshops, each with more than 500 participants were organised. The aim of the testing was to gather information and gain experience to update the Framework and improve its relevance, reliability and operability. The revised SSbD Framework, which the European Commission is presenting for public consultation is based on lessons learned during the two-year testing period. It will serve as the foundation for revising the European Commission Recommendations by the end of 2025. Public and experts can participate in the online consultation at the European Commission's [Have your Say](#) portal until **15 September 2025**.

European Biotech Act: A European consultation open

Did you know that ReBioCycle is working on developing and scaling up biological recycling, utilising both enzymes and microorganisms?

The biotech sector plays a critical role in several areas of the EU economy. It is research-driven, fast-moving and requires substantial public and private investments.

The European Commission has just launched a consultation on the shaping of the Biotech Act with a European Regulation. The Act will propose a series of measures to create an enabling environment to accelerate the transition of biotech products from laboratory to factory and to the market, while maintaining the highest safety standards for the protection of the population and the environment.

It is expected that the Biotech Act will be a European Regulation. A "regulation" is a binding legislative act. It must be applied in its entirety and uniformly across the European Union.

Have your say until 10 November 2025. Read more and submit your opinion:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14627-Biotech-Act_en

Source: European Commission.

Get to know more about ReBioCycle

Visit us: www.rebiocycle.eu

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rebiocycle/>

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/rebiocycle/>Acknowledgement of funding

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